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His Brain Is Slowly Rotting

I saw my friend and said, "Hi,"
But he did not hear me or even smile.
Oh he does not seem to see me,
He is too focused on the screen, too busy.

We go out together with our other friends,
Yet he barely gives them attention or lends
A moment to talk, a moment to be,
For he is lost in the world that he sees.

He is too busy watching online,
Scrolling endlessly, losing track of time.
It feels as though he is no longer there,
Only his body remains in the chair.

One day he stumbled while crossing the street,
His eyes on his phone instead of his feet.
The people around him called out his name,
But he never noticed until trouble came.

Another day, his family gathered near,
Yet he ignored their voices year after year.
Though surrounded by people who loved him so much,
He was too distracted to value their touch.

So let this be a lesson for you and me:
Life is more than what appears on a screen to see.
Technology is useful, but we must know when to stop,
For real moments are priceless and should never be swapped.